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EL ALCANCE GLOBAL DEL FANDANGO EN MÚSICA, CANTO Y DANZA

SPANIARDS, INDIANS, AFRICANS AND GYPSIES:
THE GLOBAL REACH OF THE FANDANGO IN MUSIC, SONG, AND
DANCE

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THE REVELS OF A YOUNG REPUBLIC: REVOLUTIONARY POSSIBILITIES OF THE FANDANGO IN TIMOTHY FLINT'S 1826 FRANCIS BERRIAN

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Resumen

Francis Berrian, de Timothy Flint (1826), la primera novela de temática latinoamericana escrita en Estados Unidos presenta a un joven de Massachusetts que rescata a la hija de un Conde de una banda de Comanches, y llega a participar en la Guerra de la Independencia de México. Un fandango en la hacienda de la mujer forma la escena central, donde “ancianos y jóvenes, padres e hijos, amos y sirvientes” se entremezclan en un baile lleno de posibilidades que anticipa una futura unión provechosa entre México y los Estados Unidos. Sin embargo, al tedioso norteamericano esta exhibición de familiaridad entre clases le incomoda, y la mexicana aristocrática le reprocha su esnobismo. Quizás, sin querer, Francis Berrian nos sugiere que las ideas de igualdad y fraternidad son mejor recibidas en una pista del México aristocrático que en la República de los Estados Unidos.

Palabras Clave:

Fandango; republicanism; democracia; Timothy Flint; *Francis Berrian*

Los Fiestas de una república joven: Las posibilidades revolucionarias del Fandango en Timothy Flint 1,826 Francis Berrian.

Abstract

Timothy Flint's 1826 *Francis Berrian*, the first novel written in the United States with a Latin American setting, features a young Massachusetts native who rescues a Conde's daughter from a band of Comanches and participates in Mexico's war for independence. A fandango at the woman's estate forms a pivotal set piece where “old and young, parents and children, masters and servants” mix in a giddy dance that anticipates a future happy union between Mexico and the United States. Yet the fastidious American recoils at this display of cross-class informality, and the titled Mexican woman chastises him for his snobbery. Perhaps inadvertently, *Francis Berrian* suggests that American ideas of equality might be better practiced on the dance floor of aristocratic Mexico than they are realized in the Republic of America.

Keywords:

Fandango; republicanism; democracy; Timothy Flint; *Francis Berrian*

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In the summer of 1826, Ohio writer and editor Timothy Flint published *Francis Berrian, or, the Mexican Patriot*, the first U.S. novel with a Spanish-American setting.¹⁾ Ostensibly a celebration of the exportability of American ideals and the universality of republicanism "in the fifty-first year of the Independence of the United States of America," as the publisher noted, the story features as its titular hero a U.S. native who assists in the deliverance of Mexico from its Spanish colonial overlords and promises, through his marriage to a Mexican noblewoman, an amicable future of pan-Americanism (Flint 1826: vol. I, 2). Through the benign influence of the United States, Mexico is bound to throw off the shackles of absolute rule and crippling superstition, her citizens learning to think and act for themselves as free people. But *Francis Berrian* never entirely trusts those people—or indeed the unwashed masses of any society, whose inclinations are seen as short-sighted and often base. Like the United States itself at the dawn of the Jacksonian period, the novel cannot quite resolve the tension between republicanism and democracy.

¹⁾ STIMSON, Frederick S. "Francis Berrian': hispanic influence on American romanticism." *Hispania* 1959, 42(4), 511. *Francis Berrian* went through two U.S. editions (Boston: Cummings, Hilliard, and Company, 1826 and Philadelphia: Key and Biddle, 1834) and two English editions (London: A.K. Newman and Company, 1834 and London: J. Cunningham, 1841). Upon the publication of the first English edition, the *Monthly Magazine, or, British Register* noted approvingly, "In plain words, these are three exceedingly original and entertaining volumes." (ANON. "Francis Berrian; or the Mexican Patriot." *Monthly magazine, or, British register*, 1834, 17[98], 226).

Author Timothy Flint's recurring set piece of the fandango—which receives thirteen mentions in the text—serves as a metaphor for this tension. From the perspective of the novel's hero, a prim and buttoned-up native of Massachusetts, the fandango is associated with riotous excess, giddy triviality, the proclivity for sport and amusement supposedly typical of the Spanish-American character, contrasting strikingly with the diligent application of the Yankee. But Flint allows his Mexican heroine a defense of the fandango that offers a sharply different reading. In her praise of the dance, the fandango represents a plea for toleration and a commitment to equality that humbles the American hero's pretenses. Her remarks suggest that American ideas of equality might be better practiced on the dance floor of aristocratic Mexico than they are realized in the Republic of America.

While the character of Francis Berrian is presented as the heir to the tradition of the Marquis de Lafayette, a foreign visitor inspired by the vision of independence and singularly efficacious in its achievement,²⁾ he is also the first literary example of a type who will dominate American interference in Latin American affairs in the 1850s—the filibuster. Berrian regards it as his special mission to make over the regions south of the U.S. border after the pattern of the United States. In the case of the novel *Francis Berrian*, that model is republicanism. Republicanism is a label that has been stuck on numerous political identities and agendas over the last two millennia, but in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries it referred to a political system based on the consent of the governed rather than imposed by the fiat of a hereditary hierarchy. In direct contrast to monarchy, an illegitimate form of government, republicanism rejected inherited privilege and celebrated freedom and civic virtue. What republicanism did not guarantee was democracy—the rule of the people.

Eighteen twenty-six, the year *Francis Berrian* was published, was a pivotal one for both Latin America and the United States. Simon Bolivar called a congress of the new states of Latin America, having recently won their own independence and formed republics along U.S. lines, and the United States was invited to participate. President John Quincy Adams accepted the invitation but vetted it before Congress—at which point a contentious debate

²⁾ Both *The North American Review* and *The United States Review and Quarterly Gazette* were dubious about Flint's fictional hero playing such a leading role among actual historical figures (ANON. "Critical Notices: Francis Berrian [Review]." *North American review*, 1827, 24[54], 210-212; ANON. "Francis Berrian; or the Mexican patriot [Review]." *The United States review and literary gazette*, 1826, 1[2], 94). In fact, Flint based his character on the historical Henry Adams Bullard, the "patriotic soldier of fortune" to whom he dedicated his novel (Flint 1826: vol. I, 3). Bullard, whom Flint had met in Louisiana, responded to an appeal by Don Jose Alvarez de Toledo to revolutionize Texas in 1813. Unlike Berrian, Bullard was not successful as a revolutionary, but he became a Louisiana legislator (BONQUOIS, Dora J. "The career of Henry Adams Bullard, Louisiana jurist, legislator, and educator." *The Louisiana historical quarterly*, 1940, 23[4], 999-1106). Joel Poinsett, later U.S. Minister to Mexico, took a similarly active, if less central, role in Chilean independence (RIPPY, Fred. *The rivalry of the United States and Great Britain over Latin America, 1808-1830*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1929, 10).

ensued, some of it spontaneous and some engineered by his political rival, Martin Van Buren.³⁾ At its conclusion Congress approved the mission to Panama, but of the two delegates sent, one died on the way and the other arrived too late to participate.⁴⁾ In the process of debate, a sizeable contingent of legislators made very public racist and anti-Catholic statements—eagerly picked up by the press—that left no doubt that republicanism was not a political baptism that would wash away the original sins of racial or religious difference.

Meanwhile the United States, celebrating the fiftieth jubilee of its own independence, was confronting its own social revolution, the dawn of Jacksonian democracy. Andrew Jackson would not be elected president for two more years, but the values he stood for—expanded access to the franchise, privileges for white men at the expense of Native Americans, African Americans, and women generally—were already mobilizing camps of supporters and critics. In some ways democracy was the natural outgrowth of republicanism: if inherited privilege was to be scuttled, why was the simple farmer not the equal of the wealthy planter or merchant? But for those who fancied themselves composed of finer clay, the leveling prospects of democracy were terrifying.

Timothy Flint's novel partakes of this ambivalence and anticipates the way new understandings of race and new conflicts over class would be discussed—and masked—in the 1830s, '40s, and '50s. In a fashion familiar to readers of fiction of the Romantic period, Flint nested his tale within a series of mediated narratives. Berrian relates his life story to an unnamed author onboard a southbound steamboat in 1825, with the author's meditations framing the story. Despite the fact that the author enthuses about Berrian's bewitching attractiveness—there is something almost homoerotic in his descriptions of his hero's features and accomplishments—both the author and Berrian himself appear to the modern reader remarkably arrogant and narrow-minded. Both share a contempt for any assembly of people not composed exclusively of the beautiful, well-educated, and gently bred. Shuddering at the "customary samples and assortments of all climes, characters, ages, and conditions" that comprise the passenger list of the typical steamboat, the author singles out his hero, whose "dress and . . . servants indicated wealth" but who seemed to be "deriving

³⁾ REMINI, Robert V. *Martin Van Buren and the making of the Democratic Party*. New York and London: Columbia University Press, 1951, 104-113. See also MALANSON, Jeffrey J. "The congressional debate over U.S. participation in the Congress of Panama, 1825-26: Washington's farewell address, Monroe's doctrine, and the fundamental principles of U.S. foreign policy." *Diplomatic History*, 2006, 30(5), 813-838 and FORBES, Robert Pierce. *The Missouri Compromise and its aftermath: slavery and the meaning of America*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2007.

⁴⁾ See for example CAYTON, Andrew R.L. "The debate over the Panama Congress and the origins of the second American party system." *The historian*, 1985, 47(2), 219-238; LEWIS, Jr., James. *The American union and the problem of neighborhood: the United States and the collapse of the Spanish empire, 1783-1829* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1998).

his resources from himself, and not drawing upon the feverish stimulants of display” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 6-7; 7).

Berrian shares with the author a distaste for the “empty and boisterous character” of the other passengers, and the two men become intimate friends (Flint 1826: vol. I, 8). When Berrian shares his life story, he displays his own prejudice against the men who staff keel-boats, who appear to him “an order of beings as different from any with which I had yet been acquainted, as though they had descended from another planet” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 25). Scarcely more familiar as members of his own species are the wood cutters who erect precarious habitations on the “greasy banks” of the Red River and who “laugh and shout, and drink and blaspheme, and utter their tale of obscenity, or, it may be, of murder, with bacchanalian joyousness . . . look upon the laughers, and see the strange fire of their eye, and you will almost believe the chilling stories of Vampyres” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 29-30).

This is contempt for social inferiors, in other words, that reaches the level of pathology. That it should be expressed by a self-appointed missionary of American values seems particularly unfortunate. Interestingly enough, this classism far exceeds the hero's xenophobia, racism, and anti-Catholicism. Although the reader is treated to scorn for credulous Papists, clownish Irish servants who talk in dialect, and “copper-colored savages” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 55), these Others are not so much individualized for particular censure as they are covered with a blanket contempt for being part of the low-born rabble.

Early in the novel, Berrian, who has decided to seek his fortune in Mexico, bravely saves Dona Martha, a Conte's daughter, from a villainous Comanche. Martha's grateful parents introduce him to the luxurious world of the Mexican nobility, establishing him in their household as a tutor of English. In conversations with his hosts, Berrian defends the superiority of the United States, where rank is based on merit rather than birth: “It is true, we have no nobility, no titled and privileged class But if you imagine we have no scale by which to estimate the difference between the wise and good, and the ignorant and vile, you deeply mistake. The homage which we pay to talents, virtue, and public services is heart-felt, and paid so much the more cheerfully, as it is not levied as a tax, and is very different from the forced observance which is awarded to titled rank on the claims of prescription” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 107). But he exhibits the inclinations of a monarchist and pays willing fealty to position. Indeed so natural does American-born Berrian consider the privileges of hierarchy that he dares not dream of marriage with Martha until he has carried out several more heroic rescues and won countless military honors. Only then does Berrian decide he is indeed worthy to court her.

The novel makes the fictional Berrian instrumental in winning Mexico's independence through his instinctive understanding of military strategy—not an easy task given what is presented as the improvidence and lack of discipline of the Mexican soldiers. Flint presents

the fandango as typical of the indolent, shortsighted approach of the Spanish and native-born Mexicans. When the first stirrings of patriotic sentiment arise, Berrian is sickened to observe that it unites “children, servants, negroes, mulattoes, samboes, Indians, domestics, and wives, of all nations and colors . . . [producing] a whole medley of sounds . . . in which reckless gaiety was the key note” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 258-9). There is no order or discipline among the Mexican Patriot forces: “Almost every night brought its ball and fandango” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 273). When orders arrive to engage with the royalist troops, many of the Patriot volunteers, having overindulged in dancing the night before, fail to show up for the call of the muster roll (Flint 1826: vol. I, 279). The fandango that celebrates Patriot victory culminates in violence between Spanish officers and their American allies (Flint 1826: vol. II, 18). Disorder, laziness, unseemly fraternization: these follow on the heels of the fandango.

While the republican Berrian heaps scorn on the shiftless citizenry, it is Martha, the daughter of a Gachupín (Spanish-born) nobleman, who turns out to have the more democratic inclinations. She instinctively understands and appreciates the ideals Berrian takes for granted. When Berrian delivers her from captivity to her parents’ estate, she is not disgusted to be surrounded by “[d]omestics, Indians, negroes, mestizos, samboes, male and female, old and young, [who] crowded round the restored daughter” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 97). She is not too proud to declare she “dearly loves the fandango” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 169). A dance to which all are invited celebrates her rescue. While Berrian turns up his nose at the Conde and Condesa and their daughter sharing the dance floor with Martha’s corpulent duenna and the family’s ill spoken Irish servant, Martha explains, ““Our national manners call for all this, and allow strangers privileges here, which would not be tolerated in any other place. . . . Will you have the goodness to walk this dance with me?”” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 152). The unbending Berrian declines her invitation, but later regrets his refusal (Flint 1826: vol. I, 152).

Berrian pays lip service to the idea that the United States is exceptional because of the access to opportunity it provides all its people. But it is Martha who is truly captivated by the idea of economic equality when she visits the United States at the end of the novel. “Accustomed as she had been to see such multitudes of beggars and *leperos*” in her native Mexico, she relishes the sight of “multitudes of fine-looking and well-dressed people of both sexes, that were thronging the streets” of Philadelphia, New York, and Baltimore (Flint 1826: vol. II, 269). Her enthusiasm echoes the remarks of other foreign visitors and immigrants who acknowledged the industry of the American people, and the laws that let

them keep what they earn.⁵⁾ Martha is quite willing to see life as a dance in which all people can take part.

Berrian, on the other hand, seems to believe equality is all very well as long as the preeminence of the truly exceptional is acknowledged and rewarded. He makes sure that his future father-in-law's estates are restored after their confiscation by an interim Mexican government, and accepts a huge estate himself as a reward for his service to the new nation. He relishes his return to the United States where he can show off his new-found wealth and noble bride. "Democratic . . . as we are in New England, no little importance is attached . . . to rank and family," he remarks (Flint 1826: vol. II, 271).

When Flint's hero takes Martha home to meet his parents at the end of the novel, he sends his servant Bryan ahead of the bridal party "with a good round sum of dollars" to be invested in redecorating the family farm and making over his family (Flint 1826: vol. II, 271). The estimable Bryan invests in both actual and figurative whitewash, and Berrian comes home to find his mother fitted out with "false 'everlastings,' false teeth, and every thing false but her maternal heart" and his father unrecognizable in a "long-tailed wig" (Flint 1826: vol. II, 274). He then treats the whole village to "invitations, and dinners, and parties without number" where the inhabitants are allowed glimpses of Berrian's bride in order to "catch her air, walk and manner" and argue about whether to address him as "Don" or "Duke, but the greater part fairly dubbed me General" (Flint 1826: vol. II, 275; 277; 275).

Berrian's extended celebration in the United States, characterized by jealousy and bewigged pretension, where "merits" are equated with dollars, contrasts jarringly with Martha's fandango in aristocratic Mexico, where "old and young, parents and children,

⁵⁾ See for example DE MIRANDA, Francisco. *The new democracy in America: travels of Francisco de Miranda in the United States, 1783-84*, translated by Judson P. WOOD; edited by John S. EZELL. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1963, 178: ". . . such is the industry and spirit which liberty inspires in these people that from a small portion of the lands they obtain enough to maintain their large families, pay heavy taxes, and live in comfort and contentment, a thousand times happier than the proprietaries of the rich mines and fertile lands of Mexico, Peru, Buenos Aires, Caracas, and the rest of the Spanish-American continent." See also CREVECOEUR, J. Hector St. John. *Letters from an American Farmer*. New York: Fox, Duffield & Company, 1904, 49-50: "The rich and the poor are not so far removed from each other as they are in Europe. . . . We are all animated with the spirit of an industry with is unfettered and unrestrained, because each person works for himself." English visitor Frances Trollope, who met Timothy Flint in Cincinnati and admired Francis Berrian, shared his scorn for the *hoi polloi*. But she too acknowledged that the United States set few obstacles in the path of acquiring wealth: "During nearly two years that I resided in Cincinnati, or its neighborhood, I neither saw a beggar, nor a man of sufficient fortune to permit his ceasing his efforts to increase it . . . this unity of purpose, backed by the spirit of enterprise, and joined with an acuteness and total absence of probity, where interest is concerned, which might set canny Yorkshire at defiance, may well go far towards obtaining its purpose." (TROLLOPE, Frances. *Domestic manners of the Americans*. New York: Alfred Knopf, 1949 [1832], 43.)

masters and servants. . . join in the same dance” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 151). Though author Timothy Flint validates the narrow-minded perspective of his hero, he allows Martha a challenge that haunts the novel and, indeed, the future American republic, where equal rights and opportunities for all people can never be taken for granted. When Berrian recoils at the ideal of taking part in a dance with his social inferiors, Martha retorts: “I should think it would be conformable to your republican notions to see the rich and the poor mixing together in the same sports” (Flint 1826: vol. I, 152). The inclusive community formed by the fandango is hardly a sustainable democracy. But through the dance, *Francis Berrian*’s author, Timothy Flint, suggests, perhaps without intending to do so, that Latin America may have something to teach the United States about creating a space where all people can participate on an equal footing.

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